

MSc GEM Course 2009/2010

Lund University

Advanced GIS Course

GIS PROJECT: INVESTIGATION OF THE LAKE VICTORIA REGION

Check Points

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Question 1: Describe the kind of information that is stored in the first 6 rows.

The initial climatic data we have in ASCII format which is text recording of the values of the annual precipitation for the whole Africa continent. The "no data" cell is valued as "-9999", so that in cells with this value we have just no data. The values "600xllcorner" and "-20yllcorner" mean starting points for the raster matrix.

In the first row we have some metadata information: total number of rows = 600, total number of columns = 480; y corner is -59.99999999996; x corner is -20; cell size=0.166667, NODATA value = -9999. The second row is filled up with "-9999" values which means we do not have data. The majority of the third, a fifth and sixth row have no values as well. In the fourth row we have values of the precipitation in each cell (mm). After converting this file from ASCII to raster format we received raster .tif map of precipitation in Africa.

Question 2: Brief description of the DEM files

IN the DEM catalogue there are two available data of GTopo30 - E020N40.DEM and E020S10.DEM. E020N40.DEM covers territory of Kenya and Uganda, and E020S10.DEM shows south-eastern part of Tanzania. DEM files contain horizontal grid spacing of 30 arc seconds (approximately 1 kilometre).

Besides, we have E020N40.HDR and E020S10.HDR files which contain information about byte order, number of rows, columns, number of bits, bands and other information. Files with extension .PRJ - E020N40.PRJ and E020S10.PRJ contain information about projection and its parameters.

Files with extension .DMW contain information about spatial extension: upper and low latitudes (e.g. 20.00416666666667 and 39.99583333333333 for E020N40 tile). Files with extension .STX are statistics files which contain information about band parameters:

e.g., for the E020N40 tile we have 1 -9999 5825 -2347.6 4873.5, which means build parameters: Band= 1, Min pixel value=-9999; Max pixel value = 5825; Mean pixel value = -2347.6, Standard Deviation = 4873.5.

Question 3: Minimum and Maximum latitude-longitude for the two DEM tiles and how these values relate to the name of the file

The name of the file E020S10.DEM means that the northern latitude in 10°S and southern latitude reaches to the 60°S; in east-west direction it stretches from 60°E to the 20°E. The total North-South extent is 50 grades.

For the file E020N40.DEM its name means that the northern border is located on the 40°N and reaches 10°S in the south. The total extent North-South is thus 50 grades.

In east-west direction it stretches from 20°E to the 60°E. The extent is 40 grades.

For the both files the East-West direction totally corresponds, and the E020S10.DEM lies exactly under the E020N40.DEM file.

Therefore, we have the band of tow consequent images stretching from North to South direction.

In both files the names mean the western border (E20) and northern border (S10 and N40 respectively).

Question 4:

The E020N40.STX file contains following information: Band 1; Min pixel value -9999; Max pixel value = 5825; Mean pixel value = -2347.6; Standard Deviation = 4873.5.

Therefore, min/max pixel values are -9999 and 5825.

The E020S10.STX file contains values: Band 1; Min pixel value = -9999; Max pixel value = 3484; Mean pixel value = -7715.5; Standard Deviation = 4438.6.

Therefore, min/max pixel values are -9999 and 3484.

According to the information from the Spatial Data Description/ Raster dataset information, in the metadata, number of bits per cell = 16 for both DEM tiles.

Number of cells on x-axis is 250, 291 on y-axis and 1 on Z for DEM_N40.

Number of cells on x-axis is 250, 34 on y-axis and 1 on Z for DEM_S10.

This means that we have vertically stretched image (it's longer from south to north than from east to west), that we can easily see on the images.

The information about pixel values is stored in Properties of the layers: Cell size = 0.050287643 for both X and Y Cell size. Pixel type: unsigned integer. Pixel depth: 16 Bits.

I set it as default value for the project, as well as the extent of the working area.

Question 5: What geographical reference system is used and which file provide this info.

Initially we had the 2 tiles of the USGS DEM map format which is a single file set of ASCII-encoded text containing numbers of coordinates and elevations. Initial Geographic reference was *WGS84*, projection - *Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area*, which is common for each DEM USGS tile.

The metadata with geo-referencing information for the images is available in .prj files.

For both files E020S10.DEM and E020N40.DEM we set up following spatial geographical reference system, common for all layers of the GIS-project: *Africa Albers Equal Area Conic* projection with standard parallels 20 and -23, central meridian 25 and Datum WGS-84.

Question 6: CON ([in_grid]>=32768, [in_grid] -65536, [in_grid])

For this calculation we used "Con" function which allows controlling the output value for each cell, based on whether the cell value evaluates to true or false in a conditional statement. If the cell evaluates to true, it will receive one value; if it evaluates to false, it receives another. In a general form it looks like *Con (<condition>, <true_expression>, <false_expression>)*. We used this expression to define correctly the diapason of the attribute values and check it up. In our case condition is that pixel values are more of equal than 32768 ($[in_grid] \geq 32768$), in this case we pick up all the pixels with too high value and subtract 65536 from them, to receive negative values and thus, to indicate water areas exactly. Otherwise we do not change pixels. Now we have indicated all pixels of the ocean area with negative elevation values.

Question 7:

First I merged both tiles of DEM file into one. Then I used CON-function to set all under-sea elevation data as negative. Then I collected all pixels with negative values by using "VALUE" ≤ 0 expression in function "select by attributes".

The total number of negative values (above -9999, below 0) is 26.696.796 pixels for the merged DEMs, located in 22.257 rows. Some rows contain several pixels with the same elevation value, but some are only one in a row. These pixels cover areas of waters where relief elevation values are below zero: the South Indian Ocean and other seas. The exact sum of all negative pixels was calculated using *Selection Statistics* in *Count Column* of the *Table of Attributes*.

Additional characteristics are shown in the statistics of the selected negative pixels:

Count: 22257 (number of rows)
Minimum: 1 (min number of pixels within row)
Maximum: 26415052 (max number of pixels within row)
Sum: 26696796 (total number of all pixels together)
Mean: 1199.478636 (mean value)
Standard Deviation: 177058.652448

Question 8:

New clipped and re-calculated through CON function DEM has now 235 columns and 348 rows.

Question 9:

The elevation of Lake Victoria above the sea level is **1133** meters. We have 2242 pixels belonging to the Lake Victoria. To re-set values of water level from -9999 to 0 we used the same CON function and the expression was the following: CON ([calc_S10.tif] = -9999, 0, [calc_S10.tif]) for the E020S10.DEM file and CON ([calc_N40.tif] = -9999, 0, [calc_N40.tif]) for the E020N40.DEM file.

Question 10:

According to the metadata info available in NASA's AFRICA LAND COVER CHARACTERISTICS DATA BASE, I used following characteristics to create and fill up the .bsq file:

```
BYTEORDER M
LAYOUT BIL
NROWS 9276
NCOLS 8350
NBANDS 1
NBITS 8
SKIPBYTES
XDIM 1000
YDIM 1000
ULXMAP -4458000
ULYMAP 4480000
```

After I set up the coordinate system for the created ESRI GRID file I had to reproject it to the Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area Projection.

I used Nearest Neighbour interpolation method for the procedure, because it is well-suited for the categorical data such a land classes or soil classes and it does not change pixel values which his very useful for such data. Besides, it is very quick and simple method for the machine.

Continuous data (like relief or precipitation), on the contrary, are much better interpolated via Bilinear or Cubic interpolation methods.

Question 11:

In raster GRID Landuse we have 16 unique attribute classes representing different types of land use.

Question 12:

The difference between the two methods is that the converting through GRID is more detailed way. *Min/Max* method has more values of cells ranging from 0 to 345487, while the "*add data*" method is changing from 0 till 16332. Visually, GRID looks more detailed as well: it has more classes and values of different pixels in the areas where tif has only one class. GRID has 32-Bit depth of pixels, while simple tif only 16-Bit.

However, Standard Deviation is higher in GRID file (3755) than in tif (177), which indicates that the data are spread out over a large range of values. Thus, GRID received by *Min/Max* method is more detailed but seems to be less exact: the variability of the pixels belonging to class N not so high.

Question 13:

The geodetic reference system information for the population data file .twf for the year 2000 are the following: *Projection GEOGRAPHIC, Spheroid CLARKE1866, Xshift =0.0000000000, Yshift=0.0000000000*. Initial spatial reference was undefined. I set up WGS84 spatial reference, and *Africa Albers Equal Area Conic* projection, which is the same as of other files in the GIS project. After the re-projection population files have Datum D_WGS_84, projection *Africa Albers Equal Area Conic*, linear units in meters, central meridian 25°, standard parallels 20° and -23°, latitude of origin – 0°.

Question 14:

The highest Population in a cell for the study area in 1990 is 220.648 persons per pixel; only one pixel has this value, located approximately in the centre of the region of interest.
The highest Population in a cell for the study area for the year 2000 is 345.487 persons per pixel. Again, it is only one pixel, and it's located in the same place.
According to its location and logic, it seems to be the city of Nairobi – the capital of Kenya.

Question 15:

The clipped raster with Population in Tanzania, Uganda and Kenya has 250 Columns and 326 Rows.

Addendum (just some illustrations)

General Questions

Question 10.1 Local and Global interpolations

Global interpolation is used for the creating a polynomial for the entire surface of the research area. Local interpolation is very sensitive for neighbourhood properties, and is used for creating a part of the entire surface, which has specified neighbourhoods, overlapping for each local polygon. E.g., local interpolation is more used for difficult relief, having very different space characteristics in each part. Therefore, parts of the entire surface must be interpolated separately to receive better results. In this exercise we used three interpolation methods: Kriging, Spline and IDW. The IDW, Nearest Neighbour and Spline method are local interpolations: they value distances between the interpolating point and its neighbourhood and they are based on the surrounding measured values. Trend Surfaces Interpolation method is a global interpolation method and it is based on general assessing the trends in the surface.

Question 10.2 Spline Interpolation

Spline gives very smooth surface of the area when interpolating. It minimizes overall roughness and extremities in the relief of the surface. Resulting values of Spline are varying from -2,051.259033 until 6,934.932617. In the practical we made 9 classes as more representative.

Question 10.3 Theoretically best possible values of ME and RMSE

In general, the lesser the errors - the better the results. The mean error is the difference between the interpolated and actual values, normalised by the total amount of points. Therefore, the best possible values of Mean Error will be close to zero, in their absolute values (regardless, with plus or minus): e.g., 0.00023 or -0.0021. The more number of total measured points and the lesser the difference between the interpolated value and measured actual – the lesser the ME. A perfect ME would be zero, 0 (no errors). The RMSE is received from the ME and is a good measure of precision. We received values about 12 and 13 in our exercise. The RMSE cannot be negative values, because they are received from root square and is sensitive to interpolation method and ME error.

Question 10.4 Table containing ME and RMSE

The best results are represented by the lowest values of the RMSE (Kriging by Cross-Validation).

Validating type	Interpolation method	ME	RMSE
Validation	IDW	0.01829	13.18
Cross-Validation	IDW	0.08312	12.81
Validation	Kriging	-0.05046	12.77
Cross-Validation	Kriging	-0.05086	12.39

Question 10.5

The attribute *Water ID* can be used for separating islands from water lakes. The value *Water ID=0* indicates islands.

Question 10.6 Remove water from land

To remove water from land we need use Raster Calculator in the Spatial Analysis, and then to extract [Land_raster] – [Water_raster].

Question 10.7 The area values for risk classes of radon distribution

The area values for the different risk classes in radon distribution that we received are:

- 13.570.000 m² for the islands (situated in the lakes) and
- 3.981.910.000 m² for the mainland of South Sweden.

Question 10.8 Spatial resolution

The best resolution in the results received we have in the case of 300 meters, because it allows us to see more detailed the relief, and shows more carefully the dynamics of the relief (even local increasing and decreasing). When comparing to the relief with 500 meters spatial resolution, the last one has more generalised visual effect, and gives us more general impression of the trends in the surface. It omits some details in the relief.

Map of Radon Distribution

Legend

- water areas (lakes)
- radon distribution class I
- radon distribution class II

0 7,500 15,000 30,000 meters

Theoretical Questions

Question 10.9 Spatial autocorrelation

Spatial autocorrelation is aimed to measure and to analyze the how much the variables are dependent with each other in a space. It means that the values of the variables are compared with each other and estimated the degree of dependency among the values. Thus, finally it shows the degree and the intensity of the relationship between observed variables in a neighbourhood. If the dependence is high – we have very correlated variables, otherwise they are not correlated.

For example, if we have a podsol type of soil, the correlation between its spread and birch forest will be high. Other example would be climate area of negative temperatures and snow spread.

Question 10.10 Points-based and line-based interpolation

Points-based and line-based interpolations are both used for interpolation the surfaces. The difference between them is in the character of the results received. By the point-based interpolation we can receive surfaces with very different patterns of local parts of the surface. Kriging, Splines are methodologically point –based interpolations. Point-based interpolation can be good in using for difficult, very billowy relief or that varying very much. Line-based interpolation is better for contour field surfaces, uniform, homogeneous horizons (e.g., geologic strata and layers) which have more trend-like character of spreading.

Question 10.11 Sensibility to outliers.

The global interpolation methods are more sensible to the outliers, because they are indifferent to the local nuances of the surface, which is not the case with local interpolation methods: the last ones are very sensitive to the neighbourhood, can good assess local relief characteristics, and therefore interpolate good a surface for the small outlier-area. In other words, local interpolation methods are more suitable for the prediction and interpolation of the local small areas, not similar to the common general surface. Global methods are much better for the one big surface without outliers or extreme unexpected values.

Question 10.12 Second order trend surface interpolation algorithm

A trend surface interpolation is a global interpolator and assumes that in general the trend of the surface is without outliers and extreme values and therefore, it produces very smooth surface showing the gradual general trend of the relief, very generalized. Second order trend surface interpolation algorithm can be used for examining the global trend, just showing the main tendency of the process dynamics. It is unsuitable for detailed analysis but can be helpful for understanding of, e.g., what is the general direction of the relief decreasing while analysing river flow directions and possible contaminants going to the flow. It can be used as good illustration for environmental estimations showing general trend of contaminations direction.

Question 10.13 Delauney triangulation for Thiessen polygons

Method of Thiessen polygons is known for its spatial distribution of points between Thiessen polygons which enables creating of triangulated network (TIN) that are made using Delauney criteria (each point of one polygon is closer to its centre than to any other polygon). Therefore, to create a triangular regular network shown at the picture I would let each triangle have two vertexes in one

line (with no unused points in between), and the third vertex placed on the same row as one of the vertexes already used. The neighbouring vertexes will be creating the next side for the adjoining triangular, jut next to the first one, etc. Thus, it will cover the whole area by the measured points and will give us a surface consisted of non-intersecting triangles.

Question 10.14. The k-values in the IDW interpolation algorithm

The k-values in the IDW interpolation algorithm mean the weight of each point that we measure. The main idea is that the more distance between that point (e.g. Y) from the interpolated point (e.g. X) – the lesser it will be important by the calculation. Vice versa, if the point Y is located very close to our X point, which value we want to estimate, the Y value will be of great importance for our estimation. K is an exponent and is calculated from the distance toward this point, Y, from the X. If will we are indifferent to the meanings we can set value 0, and if the k values are very high (close to infinity), then the values of these points will be of great importance and their values will influence the interpolated values a lot.

Question 10.15 A semi-variogram for the for the Kriging interpolation

A semivariogram describes dependence between the two points and quantifies a spatial variation and is used for the Kriging interpolation method for predicting the values. Thus, the value of variogram is the average difference in attribute (z) values between two points. If spatial autocorrelation is different in different directions, it will mean that in these different directions we will have surfaces with more billowy relief with heights lesser depending on the neighbouring height points. Thus the surface will have more difficult relief with outstanding points, pitfalls and uneven relief in generally. I think in such situation it would be better to make the research polygons lesser, to analyse them more detailed.

HAND-IN QUESTIONS

1. New Shape Dataset: Benefits and Drawbacks

a) The benefit from joining the datasets and adding the new one shape dataset instead of the changed old ones is that we can make a lot of datasets with different fields and rows, according to our queries, and then go back to the “initial” ones and make new and new queries from them again. Every time we need to join datasets it’s a good idea to save results under different reasonable name, so that we (and other people using the same project) can understand which data contains in this table. E.g., we can have table “cities” and have info about maladies, unemployment, social events in all these cities. Every time we create new dataset showing the spatial distribution of these attributes, it’s better to save new results under relevant names: “Jobs_Cities” or “Influenza_Cities” etc, but have Cities unchanged.

b) Some drawbacks by using the new shape dataset instead of changed old ones would be too bulky GIS-projects with a lot of shape-files, taking a lot of time just to realize what is where. For example, it would be more simple and easy to have all the info in one dataset if we work in small GIS-project focusing on one exact theme (say, all social characteristics).

2. Export of relate connections

Exporting the results of a relate connection is impossible compared to the results of join connection, because the “relates” is a property of ArcMap layer, which are “on-the-fly” relationships just showing the temporary connections between two tables using key column (e.g. City ID). Joins, on the contrary, allows creating new dataset and thus, we can make as many tables from reasonable joining as it is necessary.

3. Reclassification: using lookup tables and joins: benefits.

Using this technique enables adding new values of Rank New to each record. Thus, we can apply the query of the city ranking to all cities, and countries, and to combine together different queries (e.g., select cities of rank 2 – 100.000 – 1.000.000 population within Germany only, etc.). Adding new field containing reclassification without deleting previous allows returning to the old, previous classification without difficulties. Thus, if we need to create again more detailed population map, representing ranking into 5 classes, we can choose this field (column) as a key indicator for the “Select by Attributes” query. Using one classification field, common for two of more tables enables making logical SQL-queries for different available attributes. Reclassification of vector file can be also done by using the “select by attributes” tool. For example, we have initially dataset with cities from 5.000 to 5.000.000 people, but we need only middle-sized ones. We can select cities with population from 10.000 to 1.000.000 people, then creating new layer from selected features. In a new layer we can classify these cities in 3 classes: 1) 10.000-100.000, 2) 100.000 – 500.000 3) 500.000 – 1 mln. Using this method we can select only those cities we are interested in, choosing necessary ranking: from middle-sized ones, and exclude completely little towns and big cities. Reclassification of raster file can be done by using Spatial Analyst extension.

4. Map of European population

5. "Select by Location" Dialogue

Among the selection methods available in the ArcGIS we can choose 2 main methods: "Select by Location" and "Select by Attributes". In "Select by Location" we can define the conditions, from which to choose, as the following ones:

- "intersect", which means intersection of two objects
- "are within", e.g., it can be shops, partly or completely within the given district
- "touch the boundary of", e.g., the cities located on the board of the area with bad environmental situation
- "are crossed by the outline of", e.g. houses located exactly on the road – can be used to indicate the errors in topology or dislocations
- "contain" – e.g., districts that contain schools and hospitals, and those without.
- "share a line segment with", e.g. objects having two or more points in common (can be adjacent house buildings)
- "are within distance" – useful to highlight buffer zones (e.g. along the roads)

6. Selecting Procedure: identifying cities in big countries

The way of identifying cities in big countries (with population of more than 10.000.000) is "select by location", which is a SQL-based query procedure.

Another way is to make this selection is using relate tables. City table must be related to the Big_Countries table. After making selection of all big countries we can see the cities that are located on their territories. Then we can select the cities that are placed on the highlighted Big_Countries and make the new layer from the selected features (Cities_Big_Countries).

Question 1.

The graphs of the fuzzy membership function of base saturation and depth are represented by the graph of the straight line, which has constant value of 0 at the Y axis until it reaches 5 at the X axis, then increases rapidly, which shows the increase of the saturation level, and after having reached the saturation point (12.5), it remains constant at the value of 1.

Fig.1. Graph of fuzzy membership function of the base saturation

Fig.2. Graph of fuzzy membership function of the depth

Question 2.

The cross over point for the base saturation where the $\mu(x)=0.5$ is 67.5 (from the graph).

The cross over point for the base saturation where the $\mu(x)=0.5$ is 0.5 (from the graph).

Question 3.

The convex combination is a set of probability distribution of the events (e.g. points, or vectors) taken with weighted coefficients. The maximum value that is possible to obtain with the convex combination is therefore 1, because it is the linear sum of the probabilities and the maximal probability is 100%.

Question 4.

The OR operator is inappropriate for the raster layers, because when we calculate rasters, we have to include all the criteria, that we are interested in, for the assessing of the land suitability. There cannot be any trade-offs between the criteria: the land must be assessed in a complex analysis of all attributes, e.g. chemical and physical requirements, texture and moisture. Using OR would mean possible excluding of some of the characteristics from the assessment. For the land suitability assessment it is necessary to take into account all the characteristics, weighted on their importance.

Question 5.

In terms of suitability, the lower the fuzzy value, the less suitable is that parameter. However, in case if a grid cell has a low fuzzy value on only one of the soil parameters but still a high resulting fuzzy value, we would receive finally high fuzzy value, because it will be "re-compensated" by the other high values. As convex combination includes all factors of this parameter, the resulting final importance of the suitability will be high.

Question 6.

If it is necessary to receive the equal weights of the parameters, we need to divide "1", as the highest suitability value, to the number of the parameters that are included (we have 6 total), to receive an equal weights for each of them. Thus, when calculating the convex combination with all weights equal, we receive as a result of 1 divided by the 6 numbers of parameters, which is 0.16666.

Question 7.

The Convex combination function can be calculated with weighted values or with equal values of fuzzy parameters. One with weighted values gives more detailed results of land suitability than that with equal values, because the first one takes into account values of soil characteristics according to their importance (Fig.1 compare to Fig.3 gives more detailed illustration of land cover classes). If we need a large-scale thematic mapping in soil sciences, it's better to use convex combination function with weighted values. If only the general illustration of the land patterns is necessary regardless of the local variations of the soil characteristics, then we can accept equal values calculations.

Question 8.

The total areas of the grid cells with fuzzy values above 0.5 (which is above 6th class in new classification) are 46651 for the weighted convex combination and 47636 for the equal weights convex. The total area of cells with fuzzy values above 0.75 (which is above 8th class in new

classification) is 36424 for the weighted convex combination and 42716 for the equal weights convex combination. These results give good example of the illustration that the equal values convex combination function gives more coarse results and includes more pixels in the “suitable” class, while the weighted convex combination makes more scrupulous analysis of whether pixels belong to the suitable class or not. Therefore, according to the convex combination with weighted values, the total number of pixels in “suitable” class is lesser, which is more precise result.

Question 9.

A fuzzy modelling is based on the calculation of values of a membership function of each land class. It means that we assess each parcel of the study area, whether it is suitable land or not, using the chemical, soil, moisture and physical characteristics. This probability lies in the values between 0 and 1 for each land variable. These fuzzy membership values were computed using convex combination technique, both using equal weights and weighted values. Finally we received land-suitability maps illustrating assessment of the suitability of land class for wet paddy cropping. The technical part of our calculations included a convex combination, which allows trade-offs between criteria of the raster layer “texture” or “drainage”, and a min-max AND function, with no compensation between groups.

Land Suitability Classification using convex combination

Land Suitability Classification using AND operator in Fuzzy function

Land Classification using equal weights in Fuzzy function

Land Classification using equal weights in Fuzzy function

MSc GEM Course 2009/2010
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Report for the Practical 5: Topographical Modelling
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Question 1

The circumference of the Earth is about 40000 km and the original DEM resolution is 3 arc seconds. We know that the whole circle is 360° . One degree is $1/360$, and one second is, in its turn, $1/3600$ of one degree, and thus, one arcsecond is approximately $1/360 * 3600 = 1/1296000$ of the whole circle. Therefore, the approximate DEM resolution of one arcsecond in meters will be $40000000 \text{ meters} / 1296000$, which gives us the result of 30.8642 meters (approx. 31 meters). As we need to calculate 3 arcseconds, the final result will be $31 * 3 = 93$ meters. Approximately, we have resolution of **93** meters.

Question 2

To estimate slopes ArcGIS uses its *Spatial Analyst* module, which is based on mathematic calculations of the maximum rate of change between cell and its neighbours. Each cell has its place in the matrix of the cells, and is surrounded by the neighbouring cells. To calculate the slope ArcGIS computes the difference between the values of the cells (8 neighbouring cells). The bigger this difference, which means the maximal change in the elevation values between the cell and its neighbours, – the steeper the slope. And vice versa, in case of flat terrain we have low slope value and little difference between the values of the cells. The output slope raster is calculated either as percent of slope or as degree of slope. I think, advantages of this method are simplicity and logical clearness of the methodology, and also the fast calculations. The drawback can be the difficult relief structure with fast changing slopes beyond 90° , when the hills go downhill and uphill. Other problem can arise in the edge values of the pixel, because they do not have 8 neighbouring cells which can lead to errors.

Question 3

Estimation aspect is necessary for the searching of slope direction (e.g., north-facing or south-facing slopes on a mountain). To estimate aspect, ArcGIS uses *Surface Analyst*, which includes Map Algebra, i.e. estimation of the maximum rate of change in value from each cell to its neighbours in the cell values matrix. The aspect in ArcGIS is measured clockwise in degrees from 0 to 360 towards North. The value of each cell in an aspect dataset means the direction the cell's slope faces. Thus, ArcGIS estimates each value in the cells of the matrix and compare them to indicate the direction. The disadvantages can be the errors on the edges, due to the calculation techniques which suppose using the central point for the calculations, and the neighbouring points must encircle this point. Advantages are the simplicity and logical clearness of the method, and therefore quickness of the calculations.

Question 4

The Aspect criteria (only north facing, from 270° W to 90° E) fill **462424 cells**; the Slope criteria (flat ground up to 5°) fill **259643 cells**. Reclassification method to create one raster filling both criteria was following: firstly, I used Surface Analyst to create Slopes and Aspect rasters from the initial DEM

raster. Then we reclassified these two rasters respectively into two classes (0 and 1) each, according to the criteria of each of them.

Question 5

The calculated area of the potential growing sites based on the Slope and Aspect criteria is **863095500 m²**, which is 106555 cells times 8100 (cell resolution). To receive this result I multiplied both rasters of Slope and Aspect conditions (see Question 4) using Raster Calculator and received new raster filling both criteria. The areas where there was no grass have value "0", and the areas with grass – "1". To get this result I firstly reclassified both raster layer showing grass on Slopes and grass on Aspects to two classes each raster (step of Question 4). The class 1 is given to the area where the grass is growing and the class 0 – where it is not. Now we have two rasters with two classes each. After that we multiply one raster by the other, so that after the multiplication of the areas with grass (class 1) with the areas with values 0 (no grass) the result is 0; 1 by 1 is respectively 1; 0 by 0, is of course 0. So we have finally the area filling both two criteria (Slopes + Aspects). The overlay operator is *Spatial Analyst – Raster Calculation – Multiplication (*)*

Question 6

The total area of grass that cannot be seen from the roads is **172092600 m²**, which is 21246 cells times resolution of 8100 m². To receive this result, I firstly created the buffer zone of 10.000 meters on both sides along the roads. Thus, I highlighted zones which can be seen from the roads, and all other zones which cannot be seen. Then I reclassified this raster on 2 classes: "0" value – visible area along the road and "1" – invisible zones. After that I made overlay of the rasters by multiplication this new "roads visibility" raster with the raster containing all the grass growing in the area with respect to 2 criteria (Slopes + Aspect). The result is new raster with grass excluding the "along-roads" areas.

Question 7

The total area of potential growing sites that cannot be seen both from observation point and from the roads is **165612600 m²**, which is received by the calculation of the total 20446 cells times 8100. This area was computed by the multiplication of two rasters: 1) the area visibility from the observation point with classes 0 and 1, and 2) the area visibility from the roads with classes 0 and 1. The area of potential growing sites that cannot be seen from the observation point is 856615500 m², which received by multiplication of 105755 cells times 8100 m² of resolution. To receive this result I created the buffer zone of 10000 meter, and overlaid it with view-shed from the observation point. Thus, the area that cannot be seen from the observation point was received. Then this raster was multiplied by the raster showing grass growing in the total research area (with respect of Aspect and Slopes). The area of growing sites that cannot be seen from the roads is 172092600 m² (received in Question 6).

Question 8

The total area of potential growing sites that cannot be seen from 3 criteria – 1) from observation point, 2) from the roads, and 3) from the police route. The final answer for this question is received by the multiplication of the three rasters filling these criteria in each case respectively.

The final result is **141118200 m²**, which received by 17422 cells times 8100 m².

The areas of grass that cannot be seen from the observation point and from the roads are received in Question 7. The area of potential growing sites that cannot be seen from the patrol route is

708255900 m², which was received by the multiplication of the number of cells (87439) by the cell resolution 90*90 m².

Question 9 Maps

Fig.1. 3D-Map of the potential sights of growing grass. Red-coloured areas are places that cannot be seen from the patrol route, roads and observation point.

Fig.2. 3D-Map of the potential sights of growing grass. Other location of viewpoint.

Fig.3. 2D-Map of the grass growing places that cannot be seen according to 3 criteria (roads, patrol route and observation point)

Fig.4. 2D-Map showing total possible growing grass (according to aspect + slope criteria) and grass that cannot be seen from the roads, route and observation point.

Fig.5. 3D-Map of the land cover types on different heights.

Question 10

Using GIS and topographic modelling for the detecting of potential growth is, no doubt, very helpful due to the following reasons. It simplifies the searching possibilities and process in several steps. Thus, if we know exactly that the grass is really growing only on the hills with given slopes and topographic aspect, then we can just highlight the areas of interest on the map. It is really very helpful for such situations (and also in many others, e.g. like biodiversity mapping for the identifying possible growing places of the rare plants). The mask on the patrol ways and roads vicinity is also very useful, because of course, it is highly unlikely that the drags would be planted just before the police' eyes or near the roads. They are, therefore, very reasonable criteria. However, I think the problem can be just not as simple as it seems to be: e.g. the criminals can plant drags in the special places that can be even near the roads but very good hidden, or something like that. I have no ideas more, as I think the professional police may find more criteria to include. But what concerns the spatial analysis – I think, it is very reasonable and very helpful tool indeed for such tasks and situations. I personally think that the spatial analysis is the most powerful tool of GIS, and actually it is what makes GIS different from the simple “drawing maps”. Therefore, I am sure that this exercise is highly realistic. The only disadvantage would be lack of all necessary criteria. But if we include really everything possible important criteria to the spatial analysis to find that or that areas or places – it will definitely give us good and correct results. So, the question is just which criteria to include. For this given situation with drag planting may be it is necessary to include some more very specific criteria, local nuances, finally drags may not be planted there and there due to some very specific motives (incl. psychology of the criminals, some extremely specific things). But I have no ideas more about criminals, as I really never faced such problems. But using GIS and Spatial Analysis is indeed very helpful and reasonable for topographic modelling and analysis of possible spatial distribution. The powerful advantage of GIS is that in spite of sending people to find out possible places directly in the field, it saves a lot of money and time by restricting the area and excluding the evidently unnecessary areas. Thus, GIS helps to save resources of the administration by giving fast and precise results of spatial queries, which is priceless for such situation.

MSc GEM Course 2009/2010
Lund University
Advanced GIS Course
Report for the Practical 6: Coordinates and Map Projections
Student: Lemenkova Polina

PRACTICAL QUESTIONS

Question 1

When using the Identity tool we receive the coordinates written in Decimal Degrees, while in the low right corner of the map we have them in Degrees and Minutes.

Question 2

The coordinates for the city of Whitehorse are $-135^{\circ} 2.565' W$; $60^{\circ} 43,777' N$
The coordinates for the city of Shefferville are $-66^{\circ} 48.792' W$; $54^{\circ} 48' N$

Question 3

Geometric properties are used in the following projections:

- Canada Albers Equal Area Conic – equal area
- Lambert Conformal Conic - conformal
- Mercator - cylinder
- UTM - cylinder
- Ortographic - ortographic

Question 4

Basic type of the projections:

- Canada Albers Equal Area Conic - conic
- Lambert Conformal Conic - conic
- Mercator - cylindrical
- UTM – cylindrical transverse
- Ortographic – azimuthal

Question 5

At the $93^{\circ} W$

Question 6

Using UTM Zone 10 will be accurate for the Yukon Territory.

Question 7

Examples of usage of these projections:

- Canada Albers Equal Area Conic projection – for the area calculations
- Lambert Conformal Conic projection – for routes and roads mapping (preserves angles)
- Mercator projection – for navigation purposes around Canada in the coastal waters
- UTM projection – for general topographic or thematic mapping in each Zone
- Ortographic projection – for visual representation of Canada's location in the Earth planet

Area calculation of Canadian forests will be done best using Canada Albers Equal Area Conic projection. In case if we need to make local calculations within districts or regions, it is also reasonable to use relevant Zone of the UTM projection. The UTM system is not a single map projection but a series of map projections, one for each of sixty zones, therefore, it can be used for the given, not too large areas.

Question 8

Canada has the biggest area in the Mercator projection, because it has distortions in the northern parts of the Earth, located far from the equator (the standard parallel). Therefore, the Canadian area will be the greatest.

Question 9

The calculations of areas will be most correct in the equal area projection which is, e.g., *Canada Equal Area Conic*. If we need to calculate small distances, close to the meridians, it's also possible to use *UTM* projection for each Zone, as the areas near the meridians are fairly accurate represented.

Question 10

Standard parallels for the Canada Albers Equal Area Conic projection are 50° N and 70° N. They are chosen, because the most area of Canada lies in the northern latitudes between 49° N and 73° N latitudes. As the distortions between the latitudes of 50° N and 70° N will be minimal, it is correct choice of the standard parallels for Canada area.

Question 11

- B (with standard parallels 8 and 18) is more suitable for the representation of the southern parts of Canada
- C (with standard parallels 20 and 60) is more suitable for the representation of the northern parts of Canada and for the general view, as the total area is good represented
- D (with standard parallels -5 and -42) is unsuitable for the normal representation, but shows good for the total length of Canada from the west to the east. Otherwise the map is not suitable.

THEORETICAL QUESTIONS

Question 1

Examples of three map types:

1. **Conformal** projections (equal angles)
Example: *Stereographic conformal azimuthal equal-angle projection*. Stereographic projection is used for navigation in Polar Regions.
2. **Equal area** projections
Example: *Mollweide pseudocylindrical equal area projection*. It is used for demonstrating the whole world for thematic mapping in a global scale (e.g., environmental purposes).
3. **Equidistant** projections
Example: *Azimuthal equidistant projection*. It can be used for measurements along the straight lines, because the distances are correct between points along straight lines (meridians for the normal projection). It is suitable for Polar Arctic research.

Question 2

Latitude describes the placement of each object on the Earth with respect of its north-south location. Line of Latitude is the circle on the Earth (taken as a square), which is located to the north or to the south from the equator, and each point that can be placed on this circle is located at the same distance from the equator that all others. Latitude can also be defined as an angle between the zenith (line straight up at the surface) and the equator. Graphically on the Globe or maps latitudes are represented as lines of west-east horizontal direction.

Longitude describes the west-east location of the objects placed on the Earth. Graphically on the Globe or maps longitudes are represented as lines north-south vertical direction.

Longitude coordinates can be defined as an angle between the central meridian (usually, Greenwich) and current location towards west or east.

Question 3

15,7534 (received: $15 + 45/60 + 12.24/3600$)

Question 4

- 1) **Cylindrical projection** - received by the transforming all the objects on the Earth to the cylinder, wrapped around the Earth or transversing it on two secant lines. Meridians are mapped by the equal vertical lines; parallels are mapped towards north and south from the equator. There are normal, transversal and oblique forms, depending on where the standard parallel is placed and whether it is straight vertical or inclined.
- 2) **Conical projection** - received by the transforming all the objects on the Earth to the cone, wrapped around the Earth or transversing it by two lines, parallel secants. There is no distortion along the standard parallels, but distortion increases further from the chosen parallels. It suits well for the big areas, like Canada or Russia.
- 3) **Azimuthal projection** - received by the transforming all the objects places on the Earth on to the plane, either touching the Earth in one point, or transversing it by one secant line. Directions from a central point are preserved; therefore, the great circles are represented as straight lines. These projections also have radial symmetry in the scales; parallels are represented as circles, the meridians are usually the straight lines going in opposite direction from the central point.

Question 5

We need coordinate system to switch from the 3-D image of the Earth to the plane 2-D map. Projection is a set of mathematical equations allowing making this transformation. As there is no possibility to preserve both angles and areas from distortions while transforming, we need to choose optimal projection for each case. Coordinate system is a mathematical system which allows placing each point in the 2-dimensional space on the map using latitude and longitude. The exact location is usually written using degrees, minutes and seconds (but can also employ other symbols, e.g. decimal degrees etc).

Question 6

To define the projections we need the following parameters:

- a) Conic projection – two secant standard parallels (or one touching), central meridian. These parameters - secant standard parallels, central meridian - here and in other cases below mean that the plane either touches or “cuts through” the Globe, and therefore, the distortions will be zero along these lines. By moving away from the central meridian and standard parallels the distortions of this projection will arise.
- b) Cylindrical normal projection - two secant standard parallels (or one touching standard parallel), central meridian.
- c) Cylindrical transverse projection – two secant standard meridians (or one touching standard meridian), central parallel which plays the role of “standard parallel” by the normal Mercator projection, so that the parameters are the same but with opposite roles. A specific well-known case of a cylindrical transverse projection is a UTM projection, which uses a series of sixty zones, each of which is based on a specifically defined secant of the Mercator projection.
- d) Azimuthal projection – central tangent point where the plane touches the globe (the coordinates of this point – latitude and meridian). In a secant case we need to know the circle which plays the role of “standard parallel”, i.e. the distortions there are minimal. In a simple case (normal secant azimuthal projection) it is latitude of standard parallel, but in an oblique case the calculations of this circle must be more difficult.
- e) Plane Cartesian coordinate system is a simple coordinate system based on Descartes system: each point has its place and exact coordinates in a system of XY axis. Applied to a projected system we have to define the initial point of the coordinate system (0; 0) which is the “equator” and the “central meridian”. Defining these parameters we can start the Cartesian system coordinates.

Question 7

The suitability of the projection is determined by the distortions in the necessary aspect (areas, angles, shapes or distances). The lesser distortions will be on the map, the more suitable it is for the current research or use. For example, the most suitable map for the area calculations of the whole country of Canada will be Canada Albers Equal Area Conic projection. The most suitable map for the navigation is Mercator, because it preserves angles without distortions, and therefore, represents rhumb lines (showing constant angles with the meridians) by straight lines, which is perfectly for navigation purposes. Thus, it does completely depend on the use and purpose of each map, whether it is suitable or not. Thus we have to balance between the area and angles distortions to define suitability of each given map.

Fig.1. Illustration of the Canada Projections

MSc GEM Course 2009/2010

Lund University

Advanced GIS Course

Report for the Practical 7: GPS Measurements and Transformations

Student: Lemenkova Polina

Question 1

The approximate coordinates of the southernmost point of the Falsterbo peninsula are 1310226.898; 6142834.523 (in meters). The coordinates in decimal degrees are 12.814°E; 55.379°N.

Question 2

When changing projection of the data frame containing *Sweden_DCW_wrong* there is no warning, because previously we deleted the *Sweden_DCW_wrong.prj* file from the set of *Sweden_DCW_wrong* files. Therefore, these files have no information about the coordinate system, and when we change it in the data frame, where the *Sweden_DCW_wrong* file is placed, the ArcMap accepts the new coordinate system without any contradictions. But when we change the coordinate system in the frame which contains data with already defined another coordinate system, ArcMap will write a warning about the possible incompatibilities or errors. In case of *Sweden_DCW_wrong* data, we had unknown coordinate system, therefore ArcMap just set up new coordinate system for the whole frame without any questions. But if the frame contains data with coordinate system, ArcMap will write us a warning, which means "this frame contains data with already defined another coordinate system. Do you want to set up new coordinate system anyway?" By defining the coordinate system, we accept it for all data which are stored in this frame. That's why ArcMap is asking about it.

Question 3

The current coordinates for the same point of the Falsterbo peninsula measured in Question 1 are now the following: 1310060.553; 6142837.25 (in meters). In the decimal degrees we have 12.811°E; 55.379°N. Thus, the same location is now misplaced westwards.

Question 4

The displacement between the two points represented the same location in two different coordinate systems is 166.23 meters.

Fig.1. Map of isolines displacement

We took the points located in the main territory of the Lund University, and exactly in the following locations:

- 1) On the lawn between the Language and Literature Department and Physical Geography building Geocentrum I
- 2) Approximately 100 meters towards North-East from the lawn
- 3) Opposite the Physical Geography building Geocentrum I
- 4) Between the Geocentrum I and Student Health Service building
- 5) At the corner of the Language and Literature Department building, opposite the main Library

MEASUREMENT PROTOCOL				
Point-ID WAAS?	Coord.Syst./Map Datum	N/S-Coordinates	E/W Coordinates	height
1	Lat/Long – WGS84	55.70884°N	013.19995°E	56 m
	Lat/Long –RT90	55.70900°N	013.20235°E	
	Svenkst – RT90 2.5gonW	6178613 N	1336235 E	
2	Lat/Long – WGS84	55.70851°N	013.20047°E	44 m
	Lat/Long –RT90	55.70869°N	013.20289°E	
	Svenkst – RT90 2.5gonW	6178567 N	1336258 E	
3	Lat/Long – WGS84	55.70894°N	013.20145°E	60 m
	Lat/Long –RT90	55.70911°N	013.20385°E	
	Svenkst – RT90 2.5gonW	6178614 N	1336325 E	
4	Lat/Long – WGS84	55.70931°N	013.20072°E	45 m
	Lat/Long –RT90	55.70932°N	013.20070°E	
	Svenkst – RT90 2.5gonW	6178643 N	1336278 E	
5	Lat/Long – WGS84	55.70897°N	013.19848°E	72 m
	Lat/Long –RT90	55.70911°N	013.20092°E	
	Svenkst – RT90 2.5gonW	6178616 N	1336141 E	

After dividing the coordinates in three groups according to the Datum used we received 3 tables in .txt format:

Table 1. RT90 Coordinates

x	y
13.20235	55.709
13.20289	55.70869
13.20385	55.70911
13.2007	55.70932
13.20092	55.70911

Table 2. WGS84 Coordinates

x	y
13.19995	55.70884
13.20047	55.70851
13.20145	55.70894
13.20072	55.70931
13.19848	55.70897

Table 3. Svenskt RT90 2.5 gonV Coordinates

x	y
1336235	6178613
1336258	6178567
1336325	6178614
1336278	6178643
1336141	6178616

Question 5

- a) The coinciding layers are *RT90* and Svenskt coordinate system: the coordinates there are very similar, and in the medium-scale representation of the map (more than 1:4000) they coincide completely. However, in the large-scale representation (>1:4000) we can observe the little discrepancy between the layers.
- b) These layers (*RT90* and *RT90 2.5 gonV*) almost coincide because they use the same Datum *RT90*, while the *WGS 84* measurements are based on the different Datum, which is not identical to the *RT90*. Therefore, we have the gap between the locations made using different Datums.
- c) The layers having biggest difference are measurements made using *WGS84* datum and *RT90* and *RT2.5gonV* respectively. The both *RT90* and *RT2.5gonV* layers differ from the *WGS84* Datum, because of the differences in the Datums, which define the size and shape of the Earth and the orientation of the coordinate systems used to map. Due to these differences we receive different point's locations (up to 25 meters).
- d) The exact discrepancy between the measurements from the *Svenskt* coordinate system and two other points is the following: Point 1: 24.59 meters towards *WGS84* and 13.35 meters towards *RT90*; Point 2: 19.50 meters towards *WGS 84*; Point 3: 5.21 meters to *RT90* and 24.40 meters to *WGS84*; Point 4: 4.72 meters to *RT90* and 22.40 meters to *WGS84*; Point 5: 16.04 meters from the *Svenskt* coordinate to the *WGS 84*; *RT90* and *Svenskt* coordinate coincide in this case.
- e) The gap between the layers occurs due to the different Datums (*WGS 84* and *RT90*) used in the coordinate systems which place the points slightly differently. Referencing geodetic coordinates to the wrong datum can result in position errors of hundreds of meters, but we had the errors only up to 25 meters. Also weather local situation caused some inaccuracies in measurements, because the clouding conditions change constantly and in each case we have different location and number of satellites.

Fig.2. Map with GPS locations

1. a) What decimal number is the following binary 1-byte data showing?

1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Answer: 155

1. b) Write the decimal number "125" using 1-byte binary data.

0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

2. a) What decimal number is the following binary 2-byte data showing? Big-endian data formatting is used.

1st byte:

0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

2nd byte:

0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Answer: 74 (1st byte)+ 27648 (2nd byte)= 27722

2. b) Write the decimal number "46941" using 2-byte binary data. Big-endian data formatting is used.

1st byte:

0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

2nd byte:

1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

3. a) What decimal number is the following binary 2-byte data showing? Little-endian data formatting is used.

1st byte:

0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

2nd byte:

1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Answer: 1st byte+2nd byte=**15085**

1st byte: $0 \cdot 32768 + 0 \cdot 16384 + 1 \cdot 8192 + 1 \cdot 4096 + 1 \cdot 2048 + 0 \cdot 1024 + 1 \cdot 512 + 0 \cdot 256 = 14848$

2nd byte: $1 \cdot 128 + 1 \cdot 64 + 1 \cdot 32 + 0 \cdot 16 + 1 \cdot 8 + 1 \cdot 4 + 0 \cdot 2 + 1 \cdot 1 = 237$

3. b) Write the decimal number “13150” using 2-byte binary data. Little-endian data formatting is used.

1st byte:

0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

2nd byte:

0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

1st byte: $0 \cdot 32768 + 0 \cdot 16384 + 1 \cdot 8192 + 1 \cdot 4096 + 0 \cdot 2048 + 0 \cdot 1024 + 1 \cdot 512 + 1 \cdot 256 = 13056$

2nd byte: $0 \cdot 128 + 1 \cdot 64 + 0 \cdot 32 + 1 \cdot 16 + 1 \cdot 8 + 1 \cdot 4 + 1 \cdot 2 + 0 \cdot 1 = 94$

4. a) Which data types should be used for the following columns in order to minimize storage space?

ID	AREA	GMI_CNTRY	CNTRY_NAME	CITIES	POP_CNTRY	COM_STAT
1	2931.55531	RUS	Russia	9	151827600	0
2	28.15815	BLR	Belarus	6	10521400	0.1234
3	40.91131	POL	Poland	50	37911870	4

Answer:

ID: Short Integer 3-byte

CITIES: Short Integer, 3-byte

AREA: Double precision real, 24-bytes (8 times 3)

POP_CNTRY: Long Integer, 12-bytes

GMI_CNTRY: Text, 9 bytes

COM_STAT: Floating point, 12-bytes

CNTRY_NAME: Text, 21 bytes

4. b) What would be the minimum total storage space needed to save the above data? Do NOT include the column names in your calculations, only the actual data.

Answer: 84 bytes

5. Which requires the most storage space: Storing the number 1565488342123.24 or storing the short sentence: "*Jonas is awesome!*"

Answer: Sentence requires more storage space. We need 17 bytes for the sentence (15 for letter characters + 2 spaces) and 8 bytes for the number.

1) Sample points generating

Random sample points were generated using Microsoft Excel software and then the set was converted to the ArcGIS project as a table with XY-coordinates (Tools -Add XY Data). The minimal number of sample points per class should be 50 points in each class at least, and the number of total sample points should be at therefore 350 as a minimum for the seven classes. To improve quality of the research and to obtain better results in map accuracy estimations we increased this number up to 70 per class and 490 for the total number of points. Two polygon maps and points layer were converted to the raster. While converting the features to raster we needed cell size not 7.5 as suggested by the ArcGIS, but 1, because the smaller the cells size – the better the resolution and quality of the map. The cell size of 1 seems to be good resolution of the raster, enough detailed, so we chosen cell size = 1.

2) Number of sample points used for the accuracy assessment

To assess accuracy I used 70 points per class, and total number for 7 classes was therefore 490 points. The minimum number was 50 for each class, but to be sure to reach 50 for the classes with small spatial extent I chosen 70 as an appropriate number.

To assess the quality (accuracy) of the Newmap, we compared sample points from the map Newmap with those of Idrisi map. This comparison is illustrated in confusion matrix including map data points along columns and the Idrisi points in columns. Number of correctly mapped points for each class is highlighted bold in diagonal of the matrix.

Confusion matrix:

	N E W M A P							total	
	CLASS	I	II	III	IV	V	VI		VII
I D R I S I	I	1							1
	II		35				2		37
	III	1	9	89	10	6			115
	IV				11	131			142
	V			5	18	78			101
	VI				6	10	76		92
	VII							2	2
	total	2	44	105	165	94	78	2	490

3) Overall/Total accuracy

Overall accuracy is calculated using the formula: $\sum A/N$, where A is number of correctly mapped points (422) and N is the total number of points (490). Thus, according to the results I received overall accuracy= $412/490 = 0.84$, which is 84%. Overall accuracy=84%.

4) User/object accuracy

User accuracy is the probability of a point on the Newmap map to belong to the same class in the class on Idrisi map. It is calculated as \sum of correctly points divided by the total \sum of the map points.

Total number of points: 490

Total number of corrected points: 412

Number of Land Cover Class	Number of points in Newmap	Number of points in Idrisi map	Number of correct points on Newmap
1	2	1	1
2	44	37	35
3	105	115	89
4	165	142	131
5	94	101	78
6	78	92	76
7	2	2	2
Total number of points	490	490	412

After dividing the correct mapped points on the Newmap on their total number (bold) we receive **User Accuracy**:

class	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
User accuracy	50%	79%	85%	79%	83%	97%	100%

5) Producer/classification accuracy

Producer accuracy shows the probability of a chosen point on the Newmap to have the same class on the Idrisi map. Therefore, it is measured as \sum of correctly mapped points of each class divided by the \sum of the points on the Idrisi map.

Producer/Classification Accuracy:

class	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
Producer accuracy	100%	95%	77%	92%	77%	83%	100%

6) Mean Accuracy

Mean accuracy is computed as the following expression:

It is a (number of correctly mapped points) *2/ \sum (points at Newmap + points at Idrisi map) for each class. Mean accuracy always has values between producers and users accuracy.

Mean accuracy is thus calculated by formula $\{2A/(B+C)\}$ where A, B and C are the following values:

- A – number of correctly mapped points calculated below for each class; total=412
- B – number of points on Idrisi Map calculated below for each class
- C – number of points on Newmap calculated below for each class
- N – total number of points 490

CLASS I	A=1	B=1	C=2
CLASS II	A=35	B=37	C=44
CLASS III	A=89	B=115	C=105
CLASS IV	A=131	B=142	C=165
CLASS V	A=78	B=101	C=94
CLASS VI	A=76	B=92	C=78
CLASS VII	A=2	B=2	C=2

class	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
mean accuracy	66%	86%	81%	85%	80%	89%	100%

7) Areal difference

Areal difference is a difference between the number of Newmap points and the Idrisi Map points divided by the number of Idrisi Map points for each class. We need it to compare areas of different classes on the Newmap and on the Idrisi Map. Overclassification means that we have more points on the Newmap than on the old Idrisi Map. Vice versa means the opposite meaning.

class	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
Areal difference	100%	19%	-9%	16%	-7%	-15%	0%

8) Kappa coefficient of agreement

Kappa coefficient of agreement for individual classes is calculated as the following expression:

$$K = \frac{(N \cdot d - q)}{(N \cdot B - q)}$$

N- total number of points

N=490

d- Σ of correctly mapped points

q- Σ of the Idrisi points and the Newmap points

B- number of Idrisi points

CLASS I	d=1	q=3	B=1
CLASS II	d=35	q=81	B=37
CLASS III	d=89	q=220	B=115
CLASS IV	d=131	q=307	B=142
CLASS V	d=78	q=195	B=101
CLASS VI	d=76	q=170	B=92
CLASS VII	d=2	q=4	B=2

Using these data above, we calculated Kappa coefficient of agreement for individual classes:

$$\text{Kappa 1} = \frac{(490 \cdot 1 - 3)}{(490 \cdot 1 - 3)} = 1$$

$$\text{Kappa 2} = \frac{(490 \cdot 35 - 81)}{(490 \cdot 37 - 81)} = \frac{17069}{18049} = 0.95$$

$$\text{Kappa 3} = \frac{(490 \cdot 89 - 220)}{(490 \cdot 115 - 220)} = \frac{43390}{56130} = 0.77$$

$$\text{Kappa 4} = \frac{(490 \cdot 131 - 307)}{(490 \cdot 142 - 307)} = \frac{63883}{69273} = 0.92$$

$$\text{Kappa 5} = \frac{(490 \cdot 78 - 195)}{(490 \cdot 101 - 195)} = \frac{38025}{49295} = 0.77$$

$$\text{Kappa 6} = \frac{(490 \cdot 76 - 170)}{(490 \cdot 92 - 170)} = \frac{37070}{44910} = 0.82$$

$$\text{Kappa 7} = \frac{(490 \cdot 2 - 4)}{(490 \cdot 2 - 4)} = 1$$

The final results are placed on the summarizing table

class	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
Kappa	100%	95%	77%	92%	77%	82%	100%

Kappa coefficient of agreement for the entire map has to be calculated using following formula:

$$K = \frac{(N \cdot d - q)}{(N^2 - q)}$$

Kappa coefficient of agreement for the entire map: $\frac{(490 \cdot 412 - 980)}{(490^2 - 980)} = \frac{200900}{239120} = 0.84$

Kappa coefficient of agreement for the entire map= 84%.

Kappa coefficient of agreement is estimated for all classes and good illustrates whether the quality of the map is below, equal or above the random agreement. It also shows a quantitative value of this agreement. The values fall in between -1 and 1, and is calculated to the percentage thereafter.

Conclusion:

According to the final results of the current work on the map accuracy estimations, the Newmap is 84% better than by random.